

Design shift in aeronautical and aviation patents, 1880-1914

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Abstract

We have collected data on over 15,000 patents related to aeronautics and aviation filed around the world in the period from 1880 to 1914. In this work we measure the shift in topics and designs in such patents away from balloons, helicopters, and ornithopters – designs which worked at some level – toward fixed-wing airplane designs which had been shown to give better control in the air. We discuss this curated data set and the technical classifications available in it. We classify the technologies in patents based on several kinds of information: key words in their title or text, their diagrams, later CPC classifications, and the national classifications of the time. We show here that the population of patents had been shifting slowly toward fixed-wing designs and away from balloon designs since about 1895. The transition in patents is clearly detectable and well underway by 1906 when the Wrights' famous airplane patent is granted and continues to move along through 1908 when the first substantial wave of airplane-producing companies were founded around the world.

Introduction

We have collected data on over 15,000 patents worldwide related to aeronautics and aviation filed before 1918. In this work we measure the shift in topics and designs in such patents away from balloons, helicopters, and ornithopters – designs which worked at some level – toward fixed-wing airplane designs which had been shown to give better control in the air. We classify the technologies in patents based on several kinds of information: key words in their title or text, their diagrams, later CPC classifications, and the national classifications of the time. The transition in patents is detectable after 1903 when the Wrights' famous airplane patent is first filed, and is well underway by 1906 when the patent is granted, and continues to move along through 1908 when the first substantial wave of airplane-producing companies are founded around the world.

In the late 19th century growing numbers of engineers, scientists, and hobbyists experimented with flying machines. Many were drawn to visions of a flying craft that could flap its wings or soar as birds do, because this could be controlled in the air more effectively than a balloon. A technological and scientific field of “aerial navigation” gradually developed, with its own terminology that became standardized across languages. Early experimenters were largely concentrated in France, Britain, Germany, and the U.S. Some gathered in balloon clubs and societies, joining an established activity.

Aerial navigation experimenters used several fundamentally different technologies. Hot air balloons and hydrogen balloons were known to work, and some experimenters made more-steerable versions, called dirigibles. Others made models with mechanical flapping wings, called ornithopters. Still others focused on gliders with fixed wings, or propulsion with propellers that could work for either balloons or gliders.

Increasing numbers of journals and societies were devoted to ballooning, flying machines, and the challenges of “aerial navigation,” which later came to be called aeronautics. This paper examines measures of patenting activity in these areas. In the 1890s the field received new attention when the public was able to observe hang glider flights.

Dramatic public demonstrations of powered gliders around 1906 changed how many people thought about the field. The numbers of publications and patents increased sharply beginning in 1907. A wave of new airplane-making firms started up across the industrialized countries in 1908. In the next few years, airplanes were flown in dozens of exhibitions occurred and hundreds of new local aviation clubs appeared.

Patent flows show a sharp change too. Worldwide annual patent applications for aeronautics technologies more than quadrupled between 1907 and 1910. Since then, aeronautics never again represented so large a proportion of all patents. The absolute numbers of aeronautics patents declined in 1912 and fell sharply during World War I.

This paper compares attributes of patents over time to measure the shift from earlier designs to the fixed-wing design. Aeronautics was turbulent and confusing at that time. Airplanes worked, on a small scale, and an exhibition of them could draw a crowd, but they were not generally useful or robust. A new industry was beginning to appear, but it was not profitable. As far as we can tell, relatively few of the patent-filers actually worked in the new industry. Many patents were associated with technologies other than the newly dominant airplanes: balloons, dirigibles, helicopters, and ornithopters. An analysis of the patents can illuminate what the inventors were thinking, both technologically and in terms of how they would relate to the new industry. Patent data, despite some eccentricities, can provide a consistent and comparable stream of information across times and countries, even as the historical context was changing drastically.

The data show that the numbers of aeronautics-related patents grew by about 5-7% a year from the 1870s to 1906, then jumped sharply upwards until 1909-1910, then declined in or after 1911 and continued to decline in World War I. These trends were similar across countries. The spike in patents included a temporary increase in balloon and related designs and topics, but largely reflected a shift to fixed-wing airplanes. The shift to fixed-wing designs as a proportion of patents began before 1906 but continued over this period.

When examining what was different about patents in the spike period, we have only partial answers. There was some increase in the numbers of foreign filings – that is patents that substantially duplicate filings by the same inventor in another country. There is a slight increase in the number of patents explicitly associated with a company, but the overwhelming number are still filings by individual inventors who have not yet sold the rights. Few patents are funded by company research and development until World War I.

The next sections discuss what patents were filed during the period under consideration, some of the challenges in interpreting and comparing these data across time and place, and some preliminary statistical results from these comparisons.

Patents of the time

We focus on patents as indicators of creative technological effort. Aeronautics has not generally been shaped by patents as intellectual property (Mowery, 2015). Formally, a patent is a legal claim that an invention is novel, feasible, and useful. The inventor applies to a government for a patent, stating what the technology is, showing diagrams of it, and making legal claims of originality. (Inventors then did not have to demonstrate feasibility as much as they do now.) If the government grants the patent, the inventor has a right to a temporary monopoly to sell versions of the technology specified in the patent in that country. The governments number the patents and publish the inventor's description. Patents differed across countries more than they do now. There was variation in whether the patent offices tracked certain kinds of

information about each patent, and its legal applicability, its term of applicability. In this period, the systems for administering patents was becoming more standardized internationally.

In many fields, such as railroad or mining engineering, patents were generally put to commercial use within a year. Commercial sales were a smaller factor for balloons and aerial navigation. Inventors were trying to make based controlled sustained flying work, and not generally trying to make or improve an established product. We know of no patent infringement disputes in this area before the Wright brothers. So why did the inventors patent in a field such as aerial navigation? It would be helpful if they had written out their reasons for filing a patent in this area, but I cannot identify a clear exposition in the contemporary materials yet. In the absence of explicit statements, we can make some inferences.

About half of the aero patent-filers identified themselves as engineers, for many of whom filing patents was a normal professional practice. Then too, if there was a future to aviation, patentees could get some credit or make some claim to the proceeds. Perhaps more importantly, a useful invention might be a prestigious accomplishment. Patenting was sometimes glorified in that era by advocates. Thomas Edison, Alexander Graham Bell, and Nikola Tesla were recognized as founders of industries and held control of companies partly by patenting their inventions. The most important U.S. patenting agency, Munn & Company, published *Scientific American*, which emphasized that patenting was useful, constructive, and a way to help create the future (Alexander, Miller, and Pierce, 2014). The Munn publication *Practical Pointers for Patentees* (Cresee, 1902) told readers that most patents were profitable for inventors (though this could not have been true for aero patents specifically). Technical publications regularly published lists of recent patents, providing some visibility to patentees.

For aerial navigation, some early experimenters thought it was best not to patent – not to make any claim of intellectual property – at least until the technology had been shown to work. Lawrence Hargrave and Alberto Santos-Dumont took this view, which has some similarity to current “open-source” views. Once a growing industry developed, it is clearer why inventors would make an effort to patent. They could sell or license a patent’s technology much more easily than by manufacturing a product themselves. There is a complicated historical transition between early open-source phases and the industrial phase, which economists have not modelled much. An understanding of the airplane case may help understand such transitions.

Figure 1 shows a patent specification from 1893. The invention is an important glider designed by Otto Lilienthal of Berlin, with wings in roughly the shape of a soaring bird. The patent filing illustrates certain elements common in most 19th century patents: a number in the national government’s ordering scheme, a title, the patentee’s name and location or citizenship, the date it was applied for (“filed”), the date it was granted, and a diagram. This application is only two pages long, shorter than most patents of the period and much shorter than current patent filings. Its title is “Flugapparat,” meaning “flight apparatus.” Patent officials classified it by its technology, but the classification (Klasse) in this case is “Sport.” At that time, the German system did not contain any more precise aeronautics category.

Figure 1 – Otto Lilienthal’s 1893 patent

Four countries granted by far the most aeronautics patents: France, Britain, Germany, and the U.S. In each of these countries patents of all kinds, and for aeronautics in particular, grew exponentially for decades up to 1906 at rates of 5-7% per year. The spike that followed was distinct to aviation. The data make it possible to compare the number of domestic and foreign patentees to determine whether patentees came mainly from these four countries, or rather just chose to patent in these countries; such results are not yet available.

The different national patent systems had substantially different technological classification systems. These classifications are designed to organize patent office work and to help search what has been patented, and which also can be useful to historical researchers. The agenda of this poster is to compare how these different classification systems adapted to the growth and change in the important concepts and designs of aeronautics, and the appearance of a commercial activity of aviation. The data gives us some cases of patents which were classified in more than one system.

Patent data sources and their challenges

Documentation and availability of historic patents

Patent specifications and data are published by national governments. Historical data from before the early airplane period are not always online, or conveniently online. We obtained a data set from the European Patent Office through the UN’s World Intellectual Property Organization. In the earliest periods, much of the data was by necessity gathered eclectically by searching for key words, patent categories, or individuals in various online systems and compilation volumes. For 19th century patents the specification document is often not available online, and we make inferences from a brief summary or database record. For more about these issues, see Appendix A.

Most patents are first-time specifications of original work. There are two other types of patents which we count but consider as secondary. These are *additions* and *foreign filings*. An *addition* is auxiliary information about an invention filed with one national office. If approved it becomes part of the package represented by the original patent, and has the same priority date, as if it were part of the original. In our data, additions were common in France and Belgium, but uncommon elsewhere. We have identified about 450 additions so far.

Foreign filings are substantively identical to a previous patent application filed in another country. It is not always clear that a patent specification is a foreign filing; it may not explicitly refer to its predecessor. Documentation on foreign filings became clearer over time. The Paris Convention of 1883 provided an incentive to make the connection with foreign patents explicit. In uncertain cases, our guiding principle is that if the diagrams in two patents are the same, one is a foreign filing of the other; if the diagrams are not similar, they are distinct originals.¹

The set of an original (or parent) patent and its secondary patents is nowadays called a patent family. The secondary patents, also called child patents, are less important than new original (parent) patents as indicators of new inventive activity, but for this paper we count them as patents just like the first/original patent. Over time we are recording these links more explicitly and correctly in the data, and in future work can discount the secondary patents.

Relevance to aeronautics

It can be difficult to select exactly which patents were relevant to aeronautics and aviation in the period before the technological paradigm of the fixed-wing airplane was clear. Formal patent technological classifications of the time do not always identify aeronautics clearly. Classifications also differed by country, and the official patent category systems handled the new field of aeronautics differently. We apply keywords to each patent to standardize these, and for many historic patents the newer IPC and CPC technological classifications have been applied. In the case of Lilienthal's patent, the title includes the term for flight, which is one clue, and the patentee was famous for his accomplishments in aeronautics so a museum and several books explicitly listed this patent.

Second, there is underlying ambiguity or uncertainty about which patents had implications for aeronautics. It was not a field of research and development, and there were alternative models – balloons, rockets, helicopters, and flapping-wing (“ornithopter”) designs. It was not clear which of these would be really successful if any; the technology was associated with deep uncertainty.

Journals and reference works sometimes identified patents which contemporaries associated with aeronautics. Figure 2 provides an example. Like many other such lists, it helps identify which patents were relevant, but does not give much detail about each patent.

¹La Mela, Andersson, and Tell (2021) independently developed a similar definition in their research on patent families of that period.

Figure 2. List of aeronautics-related French patents from a 1901 issue of the journal L’Aérophile

Some patents focused on other fields such as automobiles or machine parts were secondarily relevant to the development of flying machines. We do not generally include these in our data unless aeronautical applications are specifically mentioned in the specification. One important category is motors or engines. We rarely include such patents, although the development of lighter power sources was important in the development of flight. Steam engines and internal combustion engines were both put to use on experimental aircraft models by 1870. Aerial propellers are certainly relevant, and we count marine propellers and windmills as marginally relevant in the data.

Quality hurdles met by each patent

The quality and length of patents varied substantially. The national patent offices had idiosyncratic rules, criteria, and fees for granting a patent. These were described from time to time in handbooks, generally written by attorneys offering international patent services. Some required each patent application to be evaluated carefully by a patent examiner for whether it met the main criteria of originality, feasibility, and usefulness. The German patent office had the highest standards.² The U.S. Patent Office also required each patent to be examined. These examiners were professionals with some technical training and experience.

The British and French offices did not have an examination system, but instead a registration system, with lower criteria. Patents would be judged acceptable for registration without a careful technical evaluation, and a fee collected. The originality of the patent would be left for disputes in court. In a patent lawsuit, a potential user of the technology could show evidence that the nominal invention was not new – that it was “prior art,” in the language of patent law, and if a plaintiff convinced the court, such a lawsuit would limit or nullify a patent’s claims.

Patents granted in the British and French systems therefore met a lower standard than those in the German system, and were more numerous than German ones. It seems likely that there was

²The high Prussian standards relative to other countries are discussed in legal and administrative detail by Donges and Selgert (2022). The German system included a tier of intellectual property claims with lower standards, more directly applicable to immediate products, called Gebrauchsmuster. We are not using this category of documents yet.

more duplication among the British- and French- granted patents, and they are less likely to be clearly written and sharply defined. There may be some way to measure or demonstrate this. We are collecting information on the practices of national patent offices.

The data on patents are on the Inventing Aviation web site at <http://econterms.net/aero>. Each patent has a wiki page with standardized data on each patent's filing year, grant year, inventors, title, and so forth. The page can also give a plain-language description of the patented invention, show images from the diagrams, links to external sources referring to the patent, and include our own classifications for it. There are also wiki pages on inventors, authors, companies, publications, and airplane clubs and societies, interlinked with the patent pages. The data make it feasible to compare patent flows across countries, across time, and across technologies.

A wiki is useful for historical research with ambiguous and uncertain data, such as misspellings, obsolete classifications, and unclear relevance to aeronautics. The data can be recorded with best guesses and notes to return to, and classifications can be changed. Variant spellings can be quickly redirected to the spelling we chose as the standard. This wiki technique can be useful to other historians who wish to get summary statistics from data in which each object is complicated, ambiguous, and interrelated with others.

Aero patent counts across countries and time

We standardize the data enough to compare patents across countries and over time on several dimensions – filing date, grant date, inventor names, applicants and assignee names, company names, titles (with English translation), keywords (in English), length of text and diagrams, and references to prior patents. A deep challenge is that many patents do not stand alone as singular accomplishments. We show some preliminary comparisons, treating foreign filings and additions just like original patents for now. Patent counts in aeronautics grew at rates of 5-7% per year in these countries up through 1906 as shown in Figure 3. This is similar to the rates of growth of patents overall, in all fields, in that period. For about a third of these, the filing year is imputed from the grant year.

Figure 3 – Patents per year related to aeronautics and aviation before the airplane industry began, showing exponential growth then a sharp increase in 1906.

Figure 4 shows estimated annual counts of publications in the field of aeronautics based on Brockett’s 1910 *Bibliography of Aeronautics*. These exclude patents, but the counts grow at a similar exponential pace, shown in figure 4. These two charts give proxy measures of the growth of aeronautics as a field, and show similar rates of change. It is rare in technological history to be able to compare growth of both patents and publications, and it helps give an insight into the technological pace of change as distinguished from the incentives to create intellectual property.

Figure 4 – Aeronautics and aviation publications per year, mainly from Brockett (1910)

Patent counts rise sharply after 1906, peaking in 1909. Figure 5 shows patent counts by filing year. A chart by the year granted is a bit more spread out. For some patents we have not yet filled in a proper grant year; in these cases we filled in the year of filing plus one; this is a plausible estimate in general. British patents peak ahead of other countries here, which may be an artefact of our imputation of filing years. After more data cleanup, the peak for British patents may match the others.

Figure 5 – Aeronautics-related patents per year for selected countries 1890-1916.

What did the inventors do to cause the spike?

The spike in patent numbers is stark. It was associated with the new technical and financial opportunities in aviation. If we could understand that better, it could give us a sense of which institutions help the invention and the industry appear. Here are some hypotheses about inventor behavior in the spike period to test in the patent data over time.

- More people were drawn to aeronautics, and filed patents in an area that is new to them -- perhaps a Gold Rush – it was new and hot and apparently feasible
- Inventors are filing more additions to patents than they did before.
- Inventors filed in more countries than before (“foreign filings”)
- In some other way, inventors filed more patents for each invention than before
- Inventors put more time or resources into aeronautics experimentation than before
- Inventors started or joined firms and built intellectual property in them
- Inventors sold more of their patent rights to firms than before
- Inventors filed patents for inventions they’d already made, or would have made anyway, but wouldn’t have patented
- Inventors filed more patents for inventions that overlapped or duplicated other patents

These are data-scientific questions, that is, questions about what the patent data can tell us. Their answers do not fully address the larger motivating questions of how there came to be an airplane and an airplane industry, and what institutions and people helped that happen. Cultivating the data to answer these questions may help address the big questions however.

Direct measures of patent documents

We gathered basic information from each patent specification. For many of the French, British, German, and American aero patents we have the numbers of text pages, of legal claims made, and of diagrams. For the sample of patents for which these are coded, German aeronautics patents had on average about two pages of text. They were shorter on average than those in

other countries, and had fewer diagrams, and made fewer legal claims. U.S. patents were the longest, averaging four pages, and they made more legal claims.

Kuhn (1962) hypothesized that when a new scientific paradigm appeared, texts about it would be lengthy as the writer had to explain the concepts at length. With time, as the paradigm became established, the texts would use a more concise standard vocabulary. In this data, however, holding country differences constant, there does not seem to have been much change in the length of aeronautical patents over time even as new concepts and designs became dominant. Perhaps the heavier-than-air paradigm still called for lengthy explanation in 1910 documents.

The text of the patents can be used in other ways eventually. Kelly, Papanikolaou, Seru, and Taddy (2020) have used the digitized text of all available U.S. patents to see which ones were influential in the sense that later patents used their terminology. According to their measures, the 1906 Wright patent is one of the most influential of all time.³

The roles of firms

The new airplane industry did not have much revenue in this period, and it is difficult to measure. Most of the revenues to the new industry appear to have come from exhibitions, not from sales of aircraft. Exhibitions were sometimes huge. Thousands of people came to the Reims 1909 exhibition. The largest of the era was in Los Angeles in early 1910. Hundreds of thousands of attendees paid about a dollar for a day's admission. Other revenues to these new firms came from contracts to sell airplanes to the national militaries, and an occasional experiment with air mail. Airplanes were first used in war in 1911-1912. Revenues were small until World War I. Bilstein (2001) cites estimates of the value of U.S. aeronautical exports as about \$100,000 in 1912 and \$226,000 in 1914. Chadeau (1987, p. 435) calculated similar rates of growth in French airplane manufacture and exports, again from a small base. Worldwide estimates of production and revenues do not seem to be available.

The early airplane makers spun off or branched in from other industries. Klepper (2009) defines spinoffs as those where a major figure in one firm came from another, and finds that by this definition spinoffs were common in the early U.S. automobile industry around the same time. It is possible to apply that definition in this data. This project has identified 300 firms or organizations which made airplanes or were significant suppliers to airplane-makers. Many appear just once in the evidence because they were assigned a patent or are referred to in a newspaper or advertisement but are not known to have continued. To the extent it is possible to identify the company founders so far, they came mainly from engineering and manufacturing industries, e.g., machine parts, engines, cars, boats, motorcycles, and rail cars.

Firms could have several potential roles in a patent filing:

- 1) A firm or other organization may be a named applicant for a patent, along perhaps with a particular inventor. In these cases, the firm probably paid for the research and development that produced the patented invention.
- 2) A firm might buy or license the intellectual property. The legal phrasing is that they would be "assigned" the patent rights.
- 3) An inventor may have hired a patent agent – either an individual or a company – to help file the patent application to the patent office. In French and British patents the role of

³ In future work we may look at the exact phrasing of aeronautical patents across countries if it becomes feasible to have all their texts digitized.

the agent was recorded on the patent document; in U.S. ones it can usually be inferred, with some difficulty, based on signatures on the diagrams. Firms may have used their own staff lawyers or other experts as patent agents, rather than hire one.

Figure 6 shows measures of the prevalence of these from a sample of our patents as a proportion of aero patents annually. Countries differ in their procedures; these are overall figures. These measures do not change much at the time of the patent spike.

Figure 6 – Roles of firms in patents, shown as percentage of coded patents each year; figures for 1880-1889, 1890-1899, and 1900-1905 are averages to avoid spikes from thin data

There is a significant rise in the number of company applicants in the World War I period, which is mirrored by a decline in the use of patent agents, possibly because companies had their own attorneys. The rate of assigning patents at the time of the grant appears to be under 10% in all periods. The overall rate of assignments of U.S. patents at the time they were granted rose from 20% to 30% during this period (Khan, 2005, p. 220). The difference may be mainly between countries, and it may be that patents in other fields were more likely to be directly applicable to production immediately. As the data fills out it will be possible to analyze this difference.

Differences across countries

Basic trends in patent flows were similar across the countries with the most patents. The other industrial countries have the same patterns, perhaps slightly delayed. Inventors were aware of work in their field in other countries. They cited inventions from in other countries quickly.

A few effects were country-specific. Patents numbers declined more in Germany and France during World War I than in other countries. The spike in aero patents was especially high in Britain, as shown in Figure 1, and seems to have been associated with especially many startup companies there, more than in other countries.

The Wright brothers filed major patent infringement lawsuits in the United States in the period of the spike. They won in the United States but not in other countries. It is not clear from the data so far that this caused differences in aviation patenting patterns between the U.S. and other countries, either in terms of numbers or technological topics. The lawsuits were famous and influential, and there may yet be a detectable effect, but in principle the lawsuits could either have encouraged inventors to work on aeronautics and apply for patents or driven them away.

Technology trends and design shift

Over time a growing fraction of these patents were associated with fixed-wing designs and with issues of stability, safety, and control in the air. However, in the spike period there was an

increase in patents for balloons and helicopters too, suggesting that the patent boom was associated with a broad sense of opportunity and relevance, not tightly bound to the newly proven technology. Classification by technology required overcoming some challenges and adding to the original data, and it has been done for a large sample but not all the patents. National systems differed (as discussed in Appendix B) and for this purpose we sometimes used the official classification but other times used the basic words and diagrams in the patent text.

Figure 7 shows the key finding, based on the proportion of our aeronautical patents which are clearly associated with either a lighter-than air design or a fixed-wing design (either gliders or powered airplanes). Many patents are in neither category, e.g. if they are helicopters, propellers, or meteorological instruments, and a few patents are “hybrids” which include both kinds of elements. From 1890 to 1918 the patents associated with lighter-than-air machines fall from about 60% of these patents to under 20%, and fixed-wing designs rose from 10% of the patents to about 50%. Both categories are growing overall, especially in the hot period of 1906-10. The transition seems to be especially quick in 1903-05, suggesting an awareness in the network of aeronautical inventors of the successful Wright experiments. Because filing dates are precise, it should be possible to produce monthly or daily versions of this graph, when the data are sharp enough to support that.

Figure 7. Technology themes associated with aeronautic patents 1890-1918

Aeronautics patents fell more in the 1914-1918 period than other categories did, presumably because airplanes were used directly in the war, so there was more reason for various actors to keep inventions secret. In peacetime patents were usually granted or rejected within two years of filing, a significant number of the patents granted in 1919 and 1920 had been filed before 1916 but approval was delayed.

Adjusting for secondary patents

We have classified whether a patent is a foreign filing or addition in many of the patent records. By default a patent is treated as a “first filing,” that is, not a foreign filing or addition. A patent is often not known to be a secondary filing until we study it specifically.

Table 1 shows estimates of how many patents are first filings by country and year. French and German patents more often make explicit that they are claiming priority from an earlier patent. It is not clear whether they are actually more likely to be derivative patents than those in the other countries. It is not plausible that only 5% of U.S. patents were secondary patents; large numbers were filed by Europeans. It will be necessary to track down whether they are substantively identical to earlier European-filed patents.

The time trends are clear, especially when we group the early years together so every percentage is computed from a sample of over 100 patents. The fraction which were primary declined from the 1880s to about 1910, then the percentage increases somewhat to 1914. There is a strong increase in primary patents during World War I, when the number of patents in this field overall is much lower. It is not clear how technology changes relate to this phenomenon. It will be possible with further study to distinguish those patents which are “additions” from those which are foreign filings, and to sharpen these estimates. Over the period, perhaps 30% of all patents were secondary, and a measure of innovation might sensibly exclude these or discount them to some degree

The decline after the spike

Why did aero patents decline after 1911? I infer that there are several overlapping explanations. The patenting frenzy went to unsustainable levels and included more duplication among patents than before. Probably once patent examiners had mastered the new field, and had time to see the filings across countries, they accepted fewer duplicates. Substantively, the patent boom showed a blossoming of alternative designs, but it declined as the basic airplane designs were increasingly standardized, and a dominant design became established. Further patenting required more specialization, more equipment, more time, so fewer inventors could do it. And revenues to the industry revenues were scant and could not sustain all the new firms -- military and postal contracts were small, passenger traffic was minimal. There were journalistic and scientific reasons to fly, but little revenue from it. Exhibition sales were the earliest source of big revenues, as huge numbers of people wanted to see an airplane fly, but by 1912 most of them had had their chance to see it. An industry shakeout took place, as many firms merged or went out of business. The numbers and sizes of exhibitions may be in decline by then, and presumably revenues too.

As World War I began, research and development expenditures on aircraft rose sharply, but patenting did not. The underlying reason, presumably, was that aeronautics had military applications, and war technologies should not be openly published by people in country A, since they could be put to use by opposing country B. Patent rights from foreigners were sometimes seized – nationalized -- by the governments at war. Some patent applications were held up in the patent offices until the war was over. Others were granted but kept secret. Our database does not have enough cases of this to make empirical statistical statements yet, but in the long run we can measure the difference between filing date and grant date across countries and time periods, to see the effect of changes in the environment including the war.

Since airplane research and development went up while patenting did not, patent numbers are a poor metric for rates of innovation during the war. Counts of aeronautics publications have the same problem – they also fell before the war and stayed low during it, as a number of aeronautics journals explicitly reduced their frequency of publication during the war.

Conclusions

The data show that the numbers of aeronautics-related patents grew by about 5-7% a year from 1880 to 1906, then jumped sharply upwards to a peak in 1909-11, then began to decline. The decline may be associated with an industry shakeout. The numbers continued to decline in World War I. These trends are similar across countries. The spike in patents includes a temporary increase in balloon and other designs and topics, but mainly is associated with a shift to fixed-wing airplanes. That is, the shift to fixed-wing designs as a proportion of patents begins before this and continued in this period. The patent-infringement lawsuits by the Wright brothers did not seem to affect the U.S. numbers compared to other countries

When inspecting what is different about the patents in the spike period from their predecessors, we have only partial answers. There is some increase in the numbers of foreign filings – that is, a patent that is substantively a duplicate of one in another country, by the same inventor. There is a slight increase in the number of patents explicitly associated with a company, but the overwhelming number still were associated with individual inventors who have not yet sold the rights. Few patents appear to be funded by company research and development until World War I.

The population of patents had been shifting slowly toward fixed-wing designs and away from balloon designs since about 1895. The transition in patents is clearly detectable and well underway by 1906 when the Wrights' famous airplane patent is granted and continues to move along through 1908 when the first substantial wave of airplane-producing companies were founded around the world.

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Appendix A: Data sources for historic patents

The European Patent Office (EPO) keeps a global database of patent documents with metadata. This is the most complete source. Julio Raffo and Intan Hamdan-Livramento of the UN's World Intellectual Property Organization made a data set from about 13,000 of these in the Patstat database available to Inventing Aviation and much of that data is now online in the wiki. These were based on searches by technical classifications.

To fill in all the desired fields requires looking at the original patent-grant documents, like the one in Figure 1. Most of these have been scanned by the national governments and are available from the public-facing EPO site <http://espacenet.com>. We search it frequently to fill in details from patents for which we have partial information, and to find others by the same inventors or with some other searchable characteristic. Google patents has many of these in a conveniently searchable way. Espacenet's coverage has been increased in recent years for the 1890-1910 period; we periodically discover historic patents there that seem not to have been there before. Espacenet does not include most patents filed before 1890.

Several national patent offices have digitized all their historic patents, or made a searchable database available. The US Patent and Trademark office has scanned all its patents back to 1836. National patent offices, especially the French Institut national de la propriété industrielle (INPI) and the German Deutsches Patent- und Markenamt (DPMA), have some searchable information on the earlier patents. The Canadian, Australian, New Zealand, and Hungarian patent offices make some information about all their historic patents available online. Some of these systems require one to know a patent number to search for its information.

Most of these governments published regular gazettes listing newly approved patents. Some of these are available online on Hathitrust, the Internet Archive, Google books, and other online sources. Published volumes from national patent offices and the U.S. Patent Office of the time listed foreign patents. These are available at the US PTO's Scientific and Technical Information Center (STIC) library. There is more to do there, but it remained closed during the covid era.

We judge whether a patent is relevant to aeronautics and aviation either by its classification or by reading it. If it refers to aircraft, we include it. In ambiguous cases we include a patent record, but mark it as only marginally related to aircraft. Our data includes some patents which are not related to aircraft if in our judgment they have certain attributes that help us – e.g. that it was filed by a person who also filed aircraft patents, and helps fill out their history, or if any secondary source has indicated that it was relevant to aeronautics. The wiki includes most relevant patents but not engines, yet.

The table below lists the countries with the most patents in our database, and the most significant sources. The main sources are Espacenet, Google patents, USPTO, and DPMA. For the oldest patents we usually don't have complete information, e.g., not the author's full name. For several countries the search is challenging, as the full inventor names are not recorded in an accessible way.

Table A1. Patent data by country

Counts of aviation-related patent records on <https://econterms.net/aero>, as of January 2023.

Country	Patents	Notes on the country's early aero patent data
France	5057	Digitized and available on espacenet back to about 1900. There are a variety of earlier sources with summaries or lists: Online INPI.fr historic patent database, searchable from http://bases-brevets19e.inpi.fr/index.asp?page=rechercheAvancee . Patents were indexed in the <i>Catalogue des brevets d'invention</i> and <i>Bulletin Officiel de la Propriété Industrielle</i> in the 1880s; and in USPTO's <i>Subject-Matter Index of Patents for Invention, France</i> (1883); <i>L'Aérophile</i> issues 1898-1905 listed aero patents specifically; <i>Aéro-Manuel</i> , 1914, lists some aero patents
United States	4804	All granted patents are digitized and available on USPTO site and on Espacenet. Original technical classifications of patent are not easily available.
Great Britain	3744	Digitized and generally available on Espacenet back to 1895-1905; they seem to be extending back further over time. Technical classifications used at the time are not easily available. Summaries of aero patents appeared in Brewer and Alexander's 1893 book, in Neilson (1910), and in many issues of <i>Aeronautical Journal</i> . <i>The Abridgements of Patent Specifications</i> listed others and some information about classification.
Germany	918	Patents began 1877; All German patents have data available at DMPA; most are digitized and online at espacenet, DPMA, or Otto-Lilienthal Museum. Regular lists of aero patents appeared in <i>Jahrbuch über die Fortschritte auf allen Gebieten der Luftschiffahrt</i> and <i>Deutsche Zeitschrift für Luftschiffahrt</i> . Alexander-Katz (1912) lists some. We exclude Gebrauchsmuster patents (quick patents) from this study for now.
Hungary	393	Hungary's patent office was distinct from Austria's. All historic patents are on the current Hungarian patent office web site, but generally not on Espacenet.
Austria	188	Patent office distinct from Hungary's. Many patents are on Espacenet; almost all are indexed by DPMA.
Belgium	154	Patents of the period are generally not online. The government published catalogues with patent summaries called <i>Recueil des Brevets d'Invention</i> volumes, available in USPTO's STIC library. Some patent indexes are available at the Joseph Cuvelier repository at the State Archives of Brussels.
Italy	118	Patents were summarized in the government gazette <i>Bollettino della proprietà intellettuale</i>
Switzerland	91	All patents have some data at DPMA. Most specifications are in espacenet
Canada	86	Granted patents documents are digitized and available from CIPO & espacenet
Spain	84	Most are indexed at espacenet and by the Oficina Española de Patentes y Marcas, but the specification documents are not often available.
Mexico	55	Drawn from Ted Beatty's data set, online (see Bibliography)
Norway	49	Patents from early aero era are not on espacenet ; titles and patentee names were available from <i>Norsk Patent Registers</i> at library in Trondheim
Denmark	33	Patents start about 1864. They are on espacenet.
New Zealand	27	Patents from early aero era are available on IPONZ web site.
Netherlands	27	Patent office restarted 1912. Patent available on the national patent office web site
Australia	20	Available from the Australian Patent Office web site
India	16	India had a patent office distinct from Great Britain's; Patent specification can be found in the online INPASS system.
A few patents from Luxembourg, Finland, Russia, Cuba, USSR, and Japan, have unique sources.		

Appendix B. Overview of patent classifications before 1915

The different national patent systems had substantially different technological classification systems. These classifications are designed to organize patent office work and to help search what has been patented, and which also can be useful to historical researchers. The agenda of this poster is to compare how these different classification systems adapted to the growth and change in the important concepts and designs of aeronautics, and the appearance of a commercial activity of aviation. The data gives us some cases of patents which were classified in more than one system.

Purposes and functions of patent classification systems

Patent agencies categorize patents by technology, function, and/or industry in the 19th century. They did this for several overlapping reasons. One reason is to simplify the search for prior art, mainly by their own examiners. It also helps them organize their own office and its workload, so they know who to assign a patent evaluation to, and can guess when asked how a particular one would have been assigned. Their own patent specialists (examiners) would become knowledgeable about particular fields. As time went on these categories were put to use in searches by patent agents, inventors, and other researchers. One reason to make searches easy was indirectly to reduce or ease later legal cases. They were not mainly trying to classify technologies for academics. Organizing a classification for *future* innovations is interesting and difficult, and it is uncertain how well it could classify a future radical invention, or macroinvention.

National patent classification systems

Documentation of the classification systems and the practices of patent offices is spotty, and one cannot always tell how a patent was classified at the time. We have found many eclectic sources however and the research continues. We have not found a full description and analysis on the subject of 19th century patent classifications yet.

There were several families of patent classifications, listed below.

French and Belgian systems

Starting in 1853, the French system had about 20 major categories, and in 1904 these were divided into more than 90 smaller categories. In our period the classification assigned to a patent was clearly shown on the granted patent specification. There were 20 categories from 1853-1904, with only minor changes over time, then these were subdivided into 99 categories.⁴ Most aeronautics and aviation patents were in the same class, 6.4, often shown as IV.4.

⁴For more detail, see Emptoz and Marechal (2002) and our wiki pages starting from http://econterms.net/aero/French_patent_classifications. There were small changes in the system over time which were not announced. INPI archivist S. Gallizia has been making records of these.

French patent specifications show the class

Figure 8. French patent documents show the technology class

German, Austrian, Scandinavian, and Dutch systems

The German patent system launched in 1877-78 with 89 categories, numbered alphabetically by their titles. It becomes more elaborated and detailed over time. Class 77, Sport, was the main category for aeronautics in the 19th century. An example is shown in Figure 1. Class 77 was then subdivided and aeronautics went into 77 group h. Nearly identical systems were adopted in Austria, Denmark, Norway, Finland, and eventually in the Netherlands, usually with some delay.

US and Canadian systems

The US had a series of patent classification systems, starting in 1836 with a 23-category system designed for the patent office to manage its own workflow. The number of categories was periodically increased. We have only partial documentation of these category systems from the 19th century.

The long-lasting aeronautics category, number 244, appeared for the first time in 1912. Before this we do not see the categories that were applied at the time on the patent itself, although the post-1912 US patent categories, IPC, and CPC categories were applied after-the-fact by specialists. It is a multiple-classification system in which a patent can be classified in multiple categories at once. The Canadian system was similar to this U.S. one, with somewhat different numbering. Canadian patents retrieved from the CIPO system show each aero patent having a single classification, however.

The UK system

The British system of the first half of the 19th century has been used in economic historical analyses, notably by Nuvolari and Tatari (2011) and a succeeding literature. However patent specification in our period does not show which class it was assigned to. The information is only in certain reports, and we have not put these in our database yet. They are not used in classification in this paper.

Other systems

Many countries had patent classification systems which were not part of the above families and are not clearly related to one another. We have some information based on our patent sample about the Australian, Belgian, Cuban, Hungarian, Italian, Swedish, Swiss, and other systems.

Each of these classified patents by technology, and in most cases there was one main category for aeronautics and aviation. Some countries or colonies did not evidently classify patents by technology. The Dutch system is inaugurated in 1912, with a category system unlike others, and which we have not fully diagnosed yet.

Present-day systems

Later international classifications IPC and CPC are huge families, with many rounds of updates. They have extraordinary detail, with tens of thousands of small categories. Many thousands are devoted just to propellers. The IPC and CPC classifications have often have been applied to some of the historic patents and we use this information when possible.

How aeronautics was incorporated into these systems over time

The usual principle for expanding a patent system to cover a new area was to add a category or to split an existing category. It was rarer and more difficult to reorganize the system overall. Thus the systems naturally become more elaborated without categories merging much (Lafond and Kim (2018), Strumsky et al (2012)).

At the beginning, there were dramatic differences in “location” and labeling of aeronautics and aviation:

- French 6.4 is “aerostation” (ballooning)
- German 77 is “Sport”
- Hungarian category broke off from railways.
- U.S. category split from pneumatics and hydraulics.
- British class 4 for aeronautics appears early, in the 1880s.

These great differences are a signal of the technological uncertainty associated with this field before the dominant design of the controllable fixed-wing airplane was established.